

TRANSLATION AND ITS CROSS-CULTURAL RELEVANCE

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ABSTRACT

The process of translation has had a significant impact on the relations of nations and countries, as it is the major factor of communication. Translation is also considered as a bridge of communication among nations that have unique culture and language. Inadequate knowledge of another culture may probably cause confusion, frustration or backlash during communication process, which can lead unsuccessful attempt of agreement. Therefore, it should be focused on creating intercultural communication in order to conduct effective conversation. This article analyzes the historical, social and cultural features of translation by combining the standards of cross-cultural communication. This article explores problems of rendering texts and speeches considering the cultural gap between distinct countries, seeks solutions and evaluates the role of interpreter in the process of translation.

Key words: intercultural communication, interlingual activity, interlingual translation, intralingual translation, intersemiotic translation, intercultural mediation, socio-cultural, intercultural sensitivity.

ANNOTATSIYA

Tarjima jarayoni xalqlar va mamlakatlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi, chunki u muloqotning asosiy omilidir. Tarjima bu o'ziga xos madaniyat va tilga ega bo'lgan millatlar o'rtasida muloqot ko'prigi hamdir. O'zga madaniyat haqida yetarli bo'lmagan bilim muloqot jarayoni davomida muvaffaqiyatsiz kelishuvga olib keluvchi chalkashlik, asabiylashish va yoki ommaviy e'tirozga sabab bo'lishi mumkin. Shu sababli samarali suxbat o'tkazish uchun madaniyatlararo muloqotni yo'lga qo'yishga e'tibor qaratish kerak. Ushbu maqola madaniyatlararo muloqot standartlari bilan birlashgan holda tarjimaning tarixiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy xususiyatlarini tahlil qiladi. Ushbu maqolada turli mamlakatlar o'rtasidagi madaniy tafovutni hisobga olgan holda matn va nutqlarni tarjima qilish muammolari o'rganiladi, yechimlar izlanadi va tarjima jarayonida tarjimoning roli baholanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot, tillararo faoliyat, tillararo tarjima, bir tilda tarjima, intersemiotik tarjima, madaniyatlararo vositachilik, ijtimoiy-madaniy, madaniyatlararo fahmlash.

INTRODUCTION

Translation is considered not only the way of communication with a help of words, but also has cross-cultural relevance in terms of intercultural communication. Communication between diverse nations, in turn, contributes to the development of various cultures, only if translator has created this communication thoroughly and effectively. It is obviously known that there will be definitely no communication, development and coordination between cultures and countries without efficient translation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The recent rapid developments in translation theories have changed the concept of translation from the status of linguistic transcoding into the wider framework of communication. Since translation is an intercultural and interlingual activity as it deals with two or more linguistic systems, which represent different cultural backgrounds. However, involving languages and cultures has the degree of distance, which differs proportionately the difficulties inherent in the translation process. Translation has become a source of transporting one culture to another, exchanging ideas and worldviews as well as intercultural communication. More generally, translation is defining the same idea in another language. Besides translation proper, which has the task of interpreting linguistic signs to a different language, there are two other forms of translation. If we follow Roman Jakobson, we will call the first form “interlingual translation” and the other two respectively: “intralingual translation” and “intersemiotic translation. According to Jakobson, they are defined as follows:

1. Intralingual translation, or ‘rewarding’ – interpretation of verbal signs by means of other signs of the same language.
2. Interlingual translation, or ‘translation proper’ – an interpretation of verbal signs by means of some other language.
3. Intersemiotic translation, or ‘transmutation’ – an interpretation of verbal signs by means of signs of non-verbal sign systems.¹⁶

Inspired and influenced by Peircean tripartites, Roman Jakobson believes “the meaning of any linguistic sign is its translation into some further, alternative sign, especially a sign ‘in which it is more fully developed’, as Pierce, the deepest inquirer into essence of signs, insistently stated”¹⁷. Translation provides a certain link between various modes communication, creates a dialogical link between two languages, imaginations, personalities as well as cultures, often dissimilar. At this point, intercultural linking of translation approaches have become highly important in the

¹⁶ Roman Jakobson, *On linguistic aspects of translation* – Cambridge, Massachusetts: 1959. – 127 p.;

¹⁷ Roman Jakobson, *On linguistic aspects of translation* – Cambridge, Massachusetts: 1959. – 233 p.;

fields of research, social and economic life concerned with the comparison of cultures and understanding of foreign languages.

DISCUSSION

The interdependence of languages and cultures enriches the meaning of the speech or text when it is used the appropriate language and adequate knowledge. While translating a speech or video, the translator realizes intimate relationships that languages have with each other and conceives the bounds of cultures that are represented in different languages. It should not be forgotten that people are alike by appearance but different by cultural backgrounds. Translating the text into another language with definitely opposite culture means having the experience of one's own language in its singularity and determination, and this capability to organize an intercultural mediation. In order to be a good translator and establish an effective communication, knowing the language and grammar rules are not enough.

Translating requires a cultural experience, extensive and encyclopedic knowledge, curiosity and high intention. It is obviously known that the culture of each nation represents this nation's identity, personality and history. Since cultures differ in their way of expression, translator should approach other culture's features conscientiously and professionally. The translator is a specialist in intercultural communication and has the status of a mediator between cultures. The target text is a cultural semiotic like the original text, therefore the translator should know how to determine the most appropriate meaning of original text in order to build adequate socio-cultural context.

It goes without saying that every single culture of the languages involved determines the source and the root of this nation and has the specific features, which only the representatives of this nation can identify. For instance, Uzbek culture based on the respect for elderly, high value of pride, honour and shame. While translating Uzbek texts or speeches, not to attach the value of these perspectives may cause the alteration of the real meaning. From this point of view, only the translator with a deep knowledge of nation's culture should translate the text. Only the professional owner of cultural knowledge can render the text using the right words and idioms.

RESULTS

Without the active role of the translator, translation, a cross-cultural communication activity, cannot be completed. In a sense, both translators and writers construct different cultures in their own environments. The translator plays an important role in promoting the communication between different cultures. Therefore,

it is necessary and meaningful to study the identity and role of the translator in the context of translation theory and cross-cultural communication.¹⁸

Sufficient translation strategy is needed in interpreting a text or speech from one language into another in order to facilitate this cross-cultural communication. Without any doubt, building the right communication between cultures requires specific skills, intercultural sensitivity and responsibility. Implementing various translation strategies is becoming necessary in order to overcome some translation problems, particularly when translating between two distinct languages like English and Uzbek. Therefore, the task of translator includes choosing a suitable strategy that will give solution to these problematic issues as well as express a translation that meets the needs of the target audience.

CONCLUSION

Culture plays a significant role in the progress of interethnic relations and in deepening and enriching the intercultural communication among nations. Thus, it is impossible to imagine our lives without exchanging ideas, experiences and cultures as well. Globalization opened the doors of countries for humanity: accordingly, it is required to visit other countries only with the awareness of their culture. Professional translator will probably be the best companion for travelling alien countries both physically and mentally.

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¹⁸ Huiling Cao, A study of translation in intercultural communication. – Francis Academy Press, UK: 2020. – 134p.;